

Settlement Pattern Features in Mountainous Countries (on the Example of the Republic of Armenia)

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Abstract

Despite the current variety in settlement patterns, mountainous countries share certain similarities in features, characteristics, trends, and issues related to settlement patterns. This article discusses the geographical peculiarities of settlement patterns in mountainous countries using the Republic of Armenia (RA) as an example. It then differentiates the types of settlement pattern territorial units in the RA, considering several principles of geographical organization, such as altitudinal zonation, the impact areas of settlement system centers, and border positions.

The analysis of settlement pattern features in mountainous countries, along with the identification of characteristics and typological zoning of settlement patterns, provides a necessary scientific basis for developing and implementing regional policies to regulate settlement patterns.

Keywords

settlement pattern, mountainous countries, Republic of Armenia, settlement system

JEL codes: R580

Introduction

Settlement pattern is a historical process of habitation and development within countries and regions, characterized by the formation and transformation of settlements and their systems. Each new stage in societal development impacts both individual settlements and the overall spatial system and network of settlements.

Settlement pattern features, development tendencies, problems, and the overall picture play a crucial role in the economic development of countries as well as in the territorial organization and governance of society. Settlement pattern is a dynamic process. On one hand, it results from a complex interaction of numerous conditions and factors; on the other hand, it drives the emergence and development of various social and economic processes.

Natural, historical, socio-economic, demographic, geopolitical, public administration, infrastructural, cultural, and other factors influence settlement patterns. Due to their diversity, priority, differences, and unique manifestations, these factors create a complex geographical mosaic of settlement patterns. However, despite this complexity, similarities in settlement pattern features, development tendencies, and problems can be observed in mountainous countries. This article focuses on these similarities using the Republic of Armenia as an example.

Methodology

To clarify the features, problems, and development tendencies of settlement patterns in mountainous countries, various sources have been examined, including published literary and analytical research, statistical data on settlements and population and the dynamics of their changes. Thematic tables were compiled, which facilitated both theoretical and empirical conclusions. The study results were also mapped, revealing and clarifying the features of spatial organization.

Descriptive, statistical, mathematical, cartographic, zoning, GIS and other methods were employed in the analysis.

Many studies focus on the influence of the natural environment on the structure and characteristics of settlements, as well as the specific features of settlement patterns in mountainous areas (Gangurde & Kumbhar 2018; Li et al. 2016; Liu et al. 2022; Hauser-Schäublin 1990; Moughtin 1984; Devitt 1979; Luo et al. 2020; Wu 2012; Key Issues ... 2004; European Parliament 2016 etc.).

Studies on the impact of globalization and the transformation of contemporary mechanisms of global economic development on mountainous countries and regions are of particular interest (Bardhan 2007; Globalization and Marginalization... 2016; ILO 2004). Countries with competitive advantages exhibit stable development trends, and their mountainous territories also show positive development trends. Conversely, countries that have taken a peripheral position in the context of the globalization of center – periphery relations demonstrate unstable and slow economic development. In these countries, mountainous areas, due to their inherent vulnerability and fragility, gradually become marginal and problematic, characterized by economic backwardness, poverty, emigration, and depopulation.

During the Soviet era in Armenia, amidst industrialization and the country's sustainable development, there was notable expansion and consolidation of both urban and rural settlements. Mountainous and high-mountainous territories were also successfully developed. However, after gaining independence and integrating into the global economy, these regions faced significant challenges due to economic shocks, deindustrialization, and substantial emigration. As a result, mountainous and high-mountainous areas have suffered and continue to suffer.

Numerous studies address the settlement patterns in Armenia and the specifics of mountainous territories. Notable contributions in this field include works by A.H. Potosyan (2017, 2018), M.G. Manasyan (2005), G.G. Ghambaryan (2019, 2020, 2022), V.A. Potosyan (2019), among others.

Study

Like any social phenomenon, settlement pattern processes occur due to the synergic interaction of external, internal, global, and local factors, as well as self-development tendencies. These processes occur in the context of direct and indirect impacts, complex and systematic interactions, cause-and-effect relationships, and both evolutionary and revolutionary transformations.

In contemporary civilization, new processes of global and regional development are emerging, along with new mechanisms of territorial organization and new geopolitical rules. These factors impact all spheres of human activity and phenomena, including structural and geographical transformations and development tendencies in settlement patterns.

Modern global processes such as globalization, urbanization, integration, scientific and technological progress, world trade and access to information, exhibit geographically uneven effects. Different geographical regions and areas, with their unique qualitative characteristics, respond differently to these phenomena. This is described as dualism, and according to some experts, it can involve triple, quadruple, or even multiple transformations (Globalization and Marginalization... 2016).

The impact of these phenomena on settlement patterns varies based on the qualitative characteristics of the area, influencing their quantitative, qualitative, and geographical changes and features. Local factors further contribute to the uniqueness of settlement patterns, particularly in mountainous regions, creating a complex geographical picture.

Despite the current diversity, mountainous countries share certain similarities in settlement pattern features and characteristics. Analyzing these features, identifying typical aspects, and establishing typological zoning based on these observations provide a necessary scientific basis for developing and implementing regional policies aimed at regulating settlement patterns.

Considering the above, the geographical features of settlement patterns in mountainous countries are illustrated using the Republic of Armenia as an example, and a generalized model of typological zoning is presented below.

Geographical features of settlement pattern of the Republic of Armenia

• *Typically, mountainous countries are characterized by a lack of usable land, uneven population distribution, and scattered settlements.*

This is due to the severe fragmentation of the mountainous terrain, significant elevation differences, steep slopes, and other natural geographical conditions. In mountainous countries, populations and most settlements are usually concentrated in foothills, river valleys, lowlands, and plateaus. The Republic of Armenia (RA) is no exception in this regard.

The RA is a typical mountainous country, occupying the northeastern part of the Armenian Highlands. The total area of the RA is 29,743 square kilometers, with an average elevation of 1,830 meters. The difference between the maximum and minimum elevations exceeds 3,700 meters (4,090 meters and 375 meters, respectively). Approximately 82% of the RA's territory consists of mountainous regions, volcanic ridges, isolated volcanic cones, and folded mountain ranges, while the remaining 18% is made up of flat plains – plateaus.

The area available for habitation and economic activity in the Republic of Armenia (RA) is relatively limited. The land with suitable natural conditions for habitation and pro-

duction is confined to slopes of approximately 16 degrees (Valesyan 1970) and elevations up to 2,000 meters, which comprises about 12,000 square kilometers, or 40% of the RA's territory. The vertical fragmentation of over two-thirds of the territory exceeds 100 meters, and in some cases, reaches up to 800 meters. Horizontal fragmentation indicators exceed 400 meters per square kilometer in 90% of the republic's territory and exceed 1,000 meters per square kilometer in 30% of the area.

Territories suitable for settlement and economic use (classified as very good, good, and average – with slopes up to 30 degrees and elevations up to 2,000 meters) constitute around 60% of the RA's territory, while unfavorable areas make up 40% (with bad areas at 25% and very bad areas at 15%).

The highly mountainous nature of the RA's territory, its small size, horizontal and vertical fragmentation, high elevation and slopes, severe climatic conditions, uneven distribution of water and land resources and seismic activity, create an anisotropic environment for the territorial organization of society (see figure 1).

Figure 1. Settlement pattern of RA. Source: by V.G. Mkhitarian and G.G. Ghambaryan

• *Settlements in mountainous countries are often at high risk for various natural disasters, such as earthquakes, landslides, floods, and others.*

For instance, the entire territory of the Republic of Armenia falls within the 8-9 Mercalli intensity scale seismic zones. A quarter of the republic's territory, where about one-third of the population resides, is extremely hazardous from a seismic perspective. Armenia has experienced several devastating earthquakes, with the most significant occurring in 1988. At the epicenter in the town of Spitak, the tremor intensity reached 9-10 points on the 12-point scale. This earthquake caused widespread destruction, affecting almost the entire northern part of the country (10,000 square kilometers), where approximately 1 million people lived. Eleven cities and 58 villages were destroyed, 21 cities and 342 villages were affected, 517,000 people were left homeless, over 25,000 lives were lost, and more than 130,000 people were injured (World Bank 2019).

Landslides, mudslides, groundwater near the earth's surface, and other geographical phenomena create unfavorable conditions for settlements in certain regions of the Republic of Armenia.

• *Typically, in mountainous countries, population density, as well as the number of people and settlements, decreases with increasing elevation, due to the more challenging living conditions and economic activities.*

However, this general pattern of settlement distribution is not absolute, as other scenarios of territorial organization exist. The formation of settlement patterns results from a synergy of natural-geographical, historical-geographical, socio-economic, and other local factors.

The Republic of Armenia exemplifies this variability. Plains and plateaus with the most favorable conditions for habitation are found at various elevations (800-2,000 meters) and exhibit higher population and settlement densities. As a result, the expected pattern of decreasing population with increasing elevation does not apply uniformly in the RA.

In the RA, inhabited areas extend from approximately 400 meters to 2,340 meters in elevation. Notably, nearly 55.9% of the population is concentrated in the **801-1,000 m** zone, which constitutes 8.3% of the RA's territory. This zone contains 21% of the settlements, including 198 villages, the capital city Yerevan, and 11 other cities. The population density in this elevation zone is 733 people per square kilometer, and rural population density is 178 people per square kilometer.

In contrast, the 1,001-1,200 m zone covers only 6.2% of the total territory and is characterized by severe surface fragmentation, steep slopes, and unfavorable conditions for habitation and economic activity. Consequently, only 4% of the population lives in this zone, with a population density of 69 people per square kilometer.

The **1,201-1,400** and **1,401-1,600 m** altitude zones make up 8.3% and 9.4% of the total territory, respectively. In these zones, 9.2% and 10.2% of the population reside, with population densities of 121 people per square kilometer and 117 people per square kilometer, respectively.

The **1,601-1,800** and **1,801-2,000 m** zones cover 10.4% and 12.8% of the total territory. These areas, which include plateaus such as the Shirak Valley, the foothills of Aragats, and the Sevan Depression, are significant settlement regions in Armenia following the Ararat Valley. In these zones, 7.2% and 8.5% of the population live. Approximately 14.9% and 16.1% of Armenia's settlements are located in these areas, with population densities of 75 people per square kilometer and 71 people per square kilometer, respectively.

The **2,001-2,250 m** altitude zone comprises 14.6% of the total territory. In this zone, both the population density and the number of settlements sharply decrease.

Above 2,250 meters, there are only three villages with a permanent population, totaling just 132 people.

As a result of the study, we arrive at the following conclusion: although areas with absolute altitudes up to 2,000 meters are generally favorable for settlement pattern, the degree of favorability decreases as altitude increases. However, another interesting trend emerges: as altitude increases, the size of these zones also expands. At elevations between 1,600 and 2,000 meters, plateaus occupy a larger portion of the territory. Notably, the Lake Sevan Basin, situated at an absolute altitude above 1,900 meters, supports a significant population (see table 1 and figure 1).

• Mountainous countries are characterized by settlements with a wide variation in population size. There is a large number of medium-sized, small, and abandoned settlements.

This is caused by the lack of favorable territories and obstacles to development. These factors limit the opportunities for settlements to grow and expand. The settlement system of the Republic of Armenia includes 49 urban settlements and 954 rural settlements (ARMSTAT 2021).

There are cities in the RA where the population is as low as a few hundred people (e.g., Dastakert with 281 people). The urban population accounts for 64% of the total, with the largest city being the capital, Yerevan, which has a population of 1.092 million. Yerevan alone concentrates 36.8% of the total population and 57.6% of the urban population of the RA (ARMSTAT 2021).

The second and third largest cities in the RA are Gyumri, with 112.1 thousand people, and Vanadzor, with 76.9 thousand people. These are considered medium-sized and large cities. However, there are no large urban settlements with populations of 250,000-500,000 people, nor are there metropolitan areas with 500,000-1 million people, indicating a polarization in the urban population distribution (see table 2).

The impact of natural factors on the rural settlement pattern is even more evident when compared to urban areas.

The rural population comprises 36% of the total population of the RA. There are 34 abandoned rural settlements, and villages with fewer than 100 residents constitute 9.2% of rural settlements, housing just 0.4% of the RA's total rural population. A significant number of rural settlements have populations of 201-500, 501-1,000, and 1,001-3,000, where 4.8%, 10.9%, and 44.4% of the rural population reside, respectively.

Additionally, there are 32 rural settlements (3.3% of the total number of villages) with populations exceeding 5,000 people, accounting for 17.7% of the rural population (see table 3). Several large rural settlements have more than 8,000 de jure residents.

• The settlements of mountainous countries are characterized by unique migration and demographic processes.

The settlement network in these areas tends to be more unstable and highly sensitive to changes in socio-economic, geopolitical, and demographic conditions (Potosyan 2017). Generally, there are many vulnerable settlements with limited opportunities for sustainable living. These settlements tend to react more severely to crises and unfavorable developments, often experiencing negative migration and demographic shifts, and in some cases, complete depopulation.

Albeit true, this statement does not necessarily imply that emigration and depopulation are typical for all mountainous countries. As analyzed in the research work "Research for REGI Committee – Cohesion in Mountainous Regions of the EU," "such a simplified picture

Table 1. The distribution of the RA territory, settlements and population by elevation zones, 2021

Elevation zones (m)	Area of the zone, %	Population distribution, %		Distribution of settlements				Population density, people/sq.km		Average population number of urban settlements	Average population number of rural settlements			
		Total	Urban	Rural	Total	Urban	Rural	Total	Rural					
												Number of settlements	Rate of total settlements, %	
Up to 800	2.1	2.6	1.7	3.9	53	6	47	5.3	12.2	4.9	130	76	5392	985.6
801-1000	8.3	55.9	68.6	35.4	210	12	198	20.9	24.5	20.8	733	178	108427	2114.1
1001-1200	6.2	4	1.6	7.8	80	3	77	8	6.1	8.1	69	52	9879	1204.7
1201-1400	8.3	9.2	8.9	9.8	93	9	84	9.3	18.4	8.8	121	49	18818	1373.6
1401-1600	9.4	10.2	9.6	11.2	152	5	147	15.1	10.2	15.4	117	49	36209	900
1601-1800	10.4	7.2	5.2	10.6	149	5	144	14.9	10.2	15.1	75	42	19546	872.3
1801-2000	12.8	8.5	3.9	15.8	162	7	155	16.1	14.3	16.2	71	51	10616	1203.3
2001-2250	14.6	2.4	0.5	5.5	101	2	99	10.1	4.1	10.4	18	16	4971	653.8
2251-2500	10.7	0.004	-	0.01	3	0	3	0.3	0	0.3	0.04	0	-	44
Above 2500	17.2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total	100	100	100	100	1003	49	954	100	100	100	99.6	42	38683.8	1239.4

Source: authors' calculations (Marzes of the Republic of Armenia 2021: 22-24)

is hardly accurate for many mountain regions, where more diversified population trends can be observed, and regional dynamics are not automatically negative”. According to the study, “the only transnational massifs with significant demographic decline between 2001 and 2011 were the Carpathians, the Balkans/South East European Mountains, and the mountains of the British Isles. Populations are rising or stable in other European mountains and, at the other end of the scale, population growth is increasingly rapid in the Pyrenees and the Alps. However, parts of these massifs are experiencing demographic decline.” The study concludes that “Europe’s mountain areas cannot generally be described as losing population” (European Parliament 2016: 19).

Table 2. RA cities by population, 2021

Largeness of settlement (people)	Number of settlement	Ratio of settlement, %	Ratio of urban population, %
Up to 2000	6	12	0.4
2001-5000	5	10	1.1
5001-10 000	11	22	4.1
10 001-20 000	15	31	12.0
20 001-50 000	9	19	14.9
50 001-100 000	1	2	4.0
100 001-250 000	1	2	5.9
250 000-500 000	-	-	-
500 000-1 000 000	-	-	-
Above 1 000 000	1	2	57.6
Total	49	100	100

Source: authors’ calculations (Marzes of the Republic of Armenia 2021: 24)

Table 3. The distribution of the RA rural population by settlements population number, 2021

Largeness of settlement (people)	Number of settlement	Ratio of settlement, %	Ratio of rural population, %
No people	34	3.6	0
Up to 50	42	4.4	0.1
51-100	46	4.8	0.3
101-200	83	8.7	1
201-500	176	18.5	4.8
501-1000	181	19	10.9
1001-3000	295	30.9	44.4
3001-5000	65	6.8	20.8
5001-7000	24	2.5	12
Above 7000	8	0.8	5.7
Total	954	100	100

Source: authors’ calculations (Marzes of the Republic of Armenia 2021: 24-28)

The demographic characteristics and dynamic trends of mountainous areas depend on various factors, including the physical-geographical features of the terrain, geographic location, economic development, economic activity characteristics, as well as the size of the country's territory, population size and trends, population density, urbanization processes, access to infrastructure and services, the effectiveness of spatial policies, and many other factors.

Moreover, within the same country, different historical periods can display varying trends in the transformation of settlement patterns, as observed in Armenia during the Soviet and post-Soviet years.

Currently, emigration and depopulation are observed in the Republic of Armenia, particularly in mountainous areas. However, these trends do not occur uniformly throughout the country. Depending on whether settlements have competitive advantages or not, and whether they are urban or rural, they respond differently to the socio-economic processes in the country. Armenia has clearly defined areas of economic growth and concentration of population—such as the Ararat Valley, Kotayk and Shirak plateaus, the foothills of Mount Aragats, and the western areas of the Lake Sevan basin—contrasted with areas of depopulation and economic decline, including the Ashotsk plateau, Tashir plateau, eastern areas of the Lake Sevan basin, Vayots Dzor, and Syunik, particularly in remote small settlements in the mountains.

Regarding mountainous rural settlements, those with competitive advantages (such as proximity to major cities, important transport routes, water bodies, extensive lands and pastures, well-developed transport and social infrastructure, or those that serve as significant tourist or agricultural centers) tend to experience population growth and economic development. In contrast, small, remote rural mountainous settlements are increasingly abandoned and depopulated, with many of them existing in the country.

The dependence of urban settlements on mountainous terrain is not decisive. Their development trends are significantly influenced by the specifics of industrial development. As a result of deindustrialization in Armenia during the post-Soviet period, there has been substantial depopulation, especially in urban areas.

For example, over the past decades, the population of Gyumri and Vanadzor has decreased by 51% and 55%, respectively, while in Yerevan, the decline was only 8% (ARMSTAT 2021).

Population growth was observed in only 5 out of 49 cities in the RA. These cities are either located in the agglomeration zone of Yerevan or in regions with low elevation, favorable geographical locations, and natural conditions. A population decline of 40% or more was recorded in 7 cities, a decrease of 20-39% in 19 cities, and a decline of 0-19% in 18 cities (table 4).

Population dynamics trends in rural settlements are not clear. As shown in the table below, since the independence of the RA, 26 settlements have been abandoned and currently have no permanent population. Additionally, 8 settlements in the study period were abandoned and remain so. Overall, the population has decreased in 372 settlements (39% of the rural settlements in the RA) and increased in 574 settlements (60% of the rural settlements in the RA). There are also 15 newly settled and resettled settlements in the country (table 5).

Studies show that the population of the RA decreased by approximately 400,000 after independence. It should be noted that this decrease primarily affected the urban population—over 400,000 people—while the rural population generally increased, despite some

Table 4. Population dynamics in RA cities in 1988-2021

Population dynamics, %	Number of settlements	Population dynamics, %	Number of settlements
-60 – -40	7	0 - 10	2
-39 – -20	19	11 - 21	3
-19 – -1	18	Total number of cities with growing population	5
Total number of cities with declining population	44	Total number of cities in RA	49

Source: authors’ calculations (Marzes of the Republic of Armenia 2021: 24-28)

Table 5. Population dynamics in RA rural settlements in 1988-2021

Population dynamics, %	Number of settlements	Population dynamics, %	Number of settlements	Population dynamics, %	Number of settlements
Depopulated – -100	26	0 – 19	204	Newly settled or resettled	15
-99 – - 80	40	20 – 39	211	Total number of rural settlements with growing population	574
-79 – -60	60	40 – 59	86	Settlements without permanent population	8
-59 – -40	55	60 – 79	32	Total number of rural settlements in RA	954
-39 – -20	55	80 – 99	8		
-19 – 0	136	100 – 200	13		
Total number of rural settlements with declining population	372	201 – 300	5		

Source: authors’ calculations (Marzes of the Republic of Armenia 2021: 24-28)

internal inconsistencies. As a result, the level of urbanization in the country has decreased from 68% to 64%.

Rural settlements, particularly those in mountainous, high-altitude, and remote frontier areas, have experienced abandonment or population decline. This issue is significant not

only because depopulation is occurring in over one-third of the country's settlements but also because there are around 88 vulnerable settlements with fewer than 100 inhabitants. The continued depopulation of these settlements could lead to their abandonment and add them to the list of the already deserted 34 settlements. Such negative changes in the settlement network reduce the opportunities for effective land use and development. Therefore, addressing this issue is both imperative and urgent, especially for a small country like Armenia with limited territorial and resource conditions.

• ***The settlements in mountainous countries are characterized by functional, production, and ethno-cultural diversity and originality, which are a result of the high degree of natural and geographical zoning.***

As a result, even territorially close settlements can exhibit significant differences in living conditions, development opportunities, and challenges, which is particularly evident in rural areas. This diversity influences agricultural specialization, work schedules, lifestyles, and folklore. For example, in the almost 30,000 square kilometers of the RA, there are more than 20 agricultural specializations and various combinations.

Rural settlements in the RA are predominantly homogeneous in terms of functional types: nearly all villages are engaged in agriculture. However, these settlements exhibit a range of production specializations, with nine distinct types identified among the various production activities. The most common specializations in the RA include beef and sheep breeding, beef cattle breeding, vegetable growing, vegetable growing combined with viticulture, viticulture, and horticulture.

• ***Mountainous countries are distinguished by a diverse range of settlement pattern types.***

River valleys are primarily characterized by a linear type of settlement pattern, where settlements of various sizes are arranged sequentially. In contrast, plains are typically characterized by a nucleated type of settlement pattern, with large and densely packed villages forming a tightly-knit network. Mountain valleys and concavities, on the other hand, often exhibit a group or dispersed type of settlement pattern.

All of these settlement pattern types can be observed in the RA. There are seven regions of rural settlement patterns, 38 local types, and 20 subtypes identified in the RA (Potosyan 2017).

The morphological characteristics of settlements include their topographical and layout features. Certain morphological types of settlements emerge from the simultaneous interaction of external conditions and the internal structure of the settlements.

In mountainous countries and regions, rural areas and settlements are notable for their diverse morphological features, as they are geographically widespread and significantly influenced by the mountainous terrain.

Based on the generalization of cartographic and field observations, A. Potosyan identifies 17 morphological types of rural settlements in the RA (Potosyan 2017).

• ***In mountainous countries, highways play a crucial role in the territorial organization of settlement patterns. These highways are often characterized by very uneven distribution, varying quality of road, significant slopes and curves, and inherent risks.***

“There has traditionally been an over-emphasis on ‘hard infrastructure’ interventions to improve accessibility. Infrastructure facilitates, but does not constitute, sustainable economic development” (European Parliament 2016: 10).

The density of the road network in the RA is also very unevenly distributed. It is dense in Yerevan and its surrounding areas but sparse in the mountainous regions and border-

lands. Despite this, all settlements in the RA are connected to the national road network. Armenia boasts a relatively well-developed road network, with asphalt roads comprising 84% of the total, a figure comparable to those in many European countries. However, a significant issue remains the condition of the roads and the distances from centers and major highways.

• *Due to the surface features of the RA and problems with transport accessibility, many settlements have weak road connections and are effectively isolated.*

Such isolation limits the potential for settlement development and increases their vulnerability. In the RA, approximately 300 settlements are isolated (with dead-end position), with 143 located in mountainous and high mountainous areas, and 93 situated in borderlands (including mountainous and high mountainous regions). The fact that 15 out of 17 abandoned mountainous and high mountainous settlements over the past three decades had isolated positions underscores the heightened vulnerability of these rural areas (Potosyan 2019).

• *Settlement pattern systems in mountainous countries are “compressed” spatially and temporally compared to those in plains.*

With equal spatial and temporal indicators, settlement pattern systems in mountainous regions cover smaller areas than in plains. This is due to the limited territory and transportation difficulties. The complexity of the terrain and natural conditions leads to narrow, winding, and often unpaved communication routes, which can be difficult to navigate and dangerous in winter and rainy weather. Consequently, transportation access to settlements becomes more challenging, with longer communication channels and increased travel times, which leads to the “compression” of settlement systems.

Many settlements in mountainous countries are thus outside the effective impact area of the settlement system. The spatiotemporal organization of the RA’s settlement systems is illustrated in the maps titled “Transport Accessibility of RA Cities (by Autoroads)” (figure 2), “Transport Accessibility of RA Cities (by Time-Spending)” (figure 3), and “Impact Potential of RA Cities” (figure 4). These maps do not include Yerevan’s settlement system, as Yerevan has developed into an agglomeration with an impact area extending beyond rural to several urban settlements. Detailed studies of transport accessibility and impact potential for Yerevan have been illustrated in separate maps, which are not included in this article.

As illustrated in Maps 2 and 3, not all settlements in the RA fall within the transport accessibility zones of up to 25 km and 30 minutes from cities. Many settlements are located outside these zones (Ghambaryan 2020).

Map 4 demonstrates that the impact potential of numerous cities is so minimal that they do not serve as local centers. The map highlights areas with influence from these centers and identifies territories outside their impact fields.

To identify the settlement impact zones, the formula proposed by Y.R. Arkhipov has been applied, namely (Arkhipov et al. 1976):

$$V = H / P,$$

where

V – is the impact field,

H – is the population number of the center,

P – is the real distance by road length.

The analysis reveals that the impact potential zones of the cities, which serve as the centers of the settlement systems in the RA. Some areas of the RA may require the establishment

Figure 2. Transport accessibility of the RA cities (by autoroads). *Source:* by G.G. Ghambaryan (Ghambaryan & Ayriyants 2019; Ghambaryan 2020)

of new centers, the enhancement of existing centers, or improvements and modernization of the road network.

• Problems related to the provision of general interest services are common in mountainous settlements.

Challenges in providing services of general interest (SGIs) are not unique to mountainous regions. Remote mountain villages encounter similar difficulties as small islands and sparsely populated areas. The profitability of SGIs in these locations is often too low for private providers to operate effectively, and public provision is costly due to the lack of economies of scale.

In mountainous regions facing these issues, require government support and development of tailored solutions that address local and regional needs. Encouraging alternative and innovative approaches can help overcome the challenges associated with providing SGIs (European Parliament 2016).

Figure 3. Transport accessibility of the RA cities (by time-spending). *Source:* by G.G. Ghambaryan (Ghambaryan & Ayriants 2019; Ghambaryan 2020)

Typological Zoning of Settlement Patterns in the Republic of Armenia

To study settlement patterns in mountainous countries effectively, it is crucial to classify settlements based on population size, demographic trends, functions, and layout structures. This classification is essential for implementing targeted state programs. However, for a more comprehensive and applicable study of settlement patterns, typological zoning of the country’s territory by settlement pattern features is necessary.

In our assessment, the following characteristics are fundamental for typological zoning of settlement patterns in mountainous countries:

1. Altitudinal Zonation
2. Impact Zones of Centers
3. Geographic Position Relative to Borders

Figure 4. Impact potential of the RA cities. *Source:* by G.G. Ghambaryan (Ghambaryan & Ayriyants 2019; Ghambaryan 2020)

This list is not exhaustive and can be expanded based on the country’s specific challenges and the scale of the study. The proposed zoning features for the Republic of Armenia are illustrative and can be adapted for use in other mountainous countries.

Considering the characteristics of territorial organization of settlement patterns, the following typological zones can be identified in mountainous countries like the RA:

1. By the features of altitudinal zonation:

- Foothills valleys zone
- Foothills regions zone
- Mountainous regions zone
- High mountainous regions zone

Foothills Valleys Zone

- Altitude Range: 400-1000 meters
- Area: More than 10.4% of the total territory of the RA
- Population: 58.5% of the country's total population
- Settlement Characteristics: This zone is characterized by favorable conditions for settlement, with medium-sized, large, and very large settlements being common. The average population of rural settlements in this zone is 1,898 people (authors' calculations based on ARMSTAT 2021 data). There are 18 urban settlements and 245 rural settlements.

Foothills Regions Zone

- Altitude Range: 1001-1700 meters
- Area: 29.1% of the country's territory
- Population: 27.1% of the total population
- Settlement Characteristics: This zone generally features medium-sized to large rural settlements in the plateaus, and small to medium-sized villages in the foothills. The average population of rural settlements in this zone is 1,064 people (authors' calculations based on ARMSTAT 2021 data). There are 18 urban settlements and 346 rural settlements.

Mountainous Regions Zone

- Altitude Range: 1701-2000 meters
- Area: 18% of the country's territory
- Population: 12% of the total population
- Settlement Characteristics: The mountainous regions exhibit more challenging conditions for settlement. This zone has fewer, often smaller, and more dispersed settlements compared to the lower altitudinal zones. There are mostly small and medium-sized rural settlements in this zone, with an average population of 1,094 (authors' calculations based on ARMSTAT 2021 data).

High Mountainous Regions Zone

- Altitude Range: more than 2001 meters
- Area: 42,5 % of the country's territory
- Population: 2,4 % of the total population
- Settlement Characteristics: It is predominantly characterized by small and medium-sized villages, with an average population of 636 (authors' calculations based on ARMSTAT 2021 data).

According to Government Resolution № 1517-N (07.09.2023) on approving the list of mountain and highland settlements of the Republic of Armenia, settlements in Armenia have been reclassified based on altitude [RA Government Resolution 2023]. Mountainous settlements are those located at elevations of 1700-2000 meters above sea level, while high-mountainous settlements are those situated at elevations above 2000 meters. There are 376 such settlements (figure 5), which are considered vulnerable. Under the law on “financial equalization” (Law of the Republic... 2016), dotations are provided to communities that include these settlements. However, there are no other support programs specifically outlined in Armenian law for these types of settlements.

Figure 5. Mountainous and high mountainous settlements of the Republic of Armenia. *Source:* by V.G. Mkhitarian and G.G. Ghambaryan

However, as shown on the map, mountainous and high-mountainous settlements vary significantly in size, development, and population dynamics. These differences indicate that these settlements have diverse needs for state care and support. Therefore, alongside the current typological approach in Armenia, it is crucial to apply a spatial approach and implement a broad range of targeted state support measures for the most vulnerable settlements. Enhancing living conditions is important, but it is equally vital to create competitive advantages for these communities.

2. By the features of impact zones of settlement pattern systems centers:

- Agglomeration zone
- Suburban area
- Peripheral zone (outside the impact zone)

The settlement pattern system is an integrated network of numerous settlements with various connections, manifested at national, regional, and local levels with complex charac-

teristics. The development of settlement pattern systems is a universal phenomenon, though there are specific features in mountainous territories.

Agglomeration Zone

In the Republic of Armenia, only one large agglomeration has formed and developed: the agglomeration of the capital, Yerevan. Similar processes were observed around the second and third-largest cities, Gyumri and Vanadzor. However, these processes significantly regressed following the devastating Spitak earthquake and post-Soviet radical changes.

The Yerevan agglomeration includes the densely developed areas of the adjacent Armavir, Ararat, Aragatsotn, and Kotayk marzes. It encompasses an additional 15 cities, of which 3 are large and 12 are medium-sized. During the Soviet era, there were strong production connections between these settlements within a high socio-economic development environment. Currently, despite increased local self-governance, due to deindustrialization these connections have weakened, though the population concentration remains high. The agglomeration of Yerevan houses 66% of the urban and 44% of the rural population of the RA.

Suburban Area

Approximately 65% of rural settlements are located within the impact zone of urban settlements in the RA. Notably, over 60% of the total rural population resides in the villages surrounding Yerevan, Gyumri, and Vanadzor.

The role of cities as “growth centers” varies in their relationship with suburban territories over different periods of development. Small and medium-sized cities, often in the early stages of development, experience centralization processes. During these stages, cities tend to absorb energy, labor, material, and information resources from adjacent areas. This leads to depopulation in the surrounding suburban areas (Ghambaryan 2020). The negative impact of such centers has been observed and discussed by researchers since the mid-20th century (Myrdal 1972).

In contrast, large cities, metropolitan areas, and cities with populations exceeding one million are in more advanced stages of development. In these cases, centralization processes occur alongside decentralization processes, which enhance the positive impact of cities on their surrounding areas. This results in the formation of more developed suburban areas (Ghambaryan 2020).

In essence, there are both direct and inverse connections between a settlement pattern center and its area of impact. In the early stages of development, direct connections are predominant, leading to increased polarization. Conversely, in the later stages of a center’s development, inverse connections become more prevalent, resulting in a more balanced impact area. This relationship underscores the connection between a center’s level of development and its impact area: “as a city develops, so, as a rule, do the villages under its influence. Without a developed center, there can be no developed suburban area” (Centr i periferija... 1991: 38). It is not coincidental that rural depopulation often occurs around small, declining cities, while relatively favorable rural areas are typically located near large, growing cities (Ghambaryan 2020).

Peripheral Zone (Outside the Impact Zone)

This zone includes areas that are outside the direct impact of major urban centers, often characterized by less developed infrastructure and weaker connections to the core settlement systems. Approximately 35% of rural settlements in the Republic of Armenia are situa-

ted in the weak impact zone of urban settlements or outside of it entirely. These settlements are predominantly located in mountainous, high mountainous, and borderland areas. They are particularly vulnerable and require state intervention and reform.

Given these conditions, one of the five factors used to calculate the dotations allocated to communities under the “financial equalization” law is the coefficient of transport accessibility. This coefficient measures the average distances from communities to the capital, regional centers, and former district centers. However, regional policy does not give sufficient attention to peripheral territories. Locally, peripheral areas include all settlements located outside the impact zone of the centre of the settlement pattern system (figure 6). The size of this influence zone varies depending on the size of the center and the distance to the settlements. Alternatively, peripheral areas are also defined as all settlements beyond a 30-minute accessibility from the center of the settlement pattern system (figure 7). This

Figure 6. Settlement pattern and impact potential of the RA cities. *Source:* by V.G. Mkhitarian and G.G. Ghambaryan

Figure 7. Settlement pattern and transport accessibility of the RA cities (by time-spending). *Source:* by V.G. Mkhitarian and G.G. Ghambaryan

definition of peripheral settlements underscores the need for zonation and targeted policies to promote equalization and economic development.

3. By Geographical Location to Borders:

- Internal Zone
- Border Zone

In the current geopolitical context of the South Caucasus, zoning settlement patterns by their geographical location relative to border areas is crucial for the Republic of Armenia.

The bordering layer of Armenia, which is the area within 1 km of the state border, covers 1,431 km², or 4.8% of the country’s total area. The border zone, defined as the area within 5 km of the state border, encompasses 7,155 km², or 24.0% of the total territory. In the bordering layer, there are 4 cities and 59 villages with a combined population of around 150,000. In the border zone, there are 9 cities and 200 rural settlements with a total population of 350,000 (General Project... 2002).

The characteristics, development opportunities, and problems of settlements in these zones vary significantly depending on the nature of the borders—whether they are open or closed, neighborly or conflictual. This distinction is particularly important in the context of closed borders and conflicts with neighboring countries. From a security perspective, the borders with Azerbaijan, including Nakhijevan, pose significant challenges, while the borders with Turkey are partially problematic. Specifically, the border with Azerbaijan, including Nakhijevan, constitutes about 62% of Armenia’s border length, while the border with Turkey accounts for about 23%.

According to Government Resolution № 713 (RA Government Resolution... 1998), there are 211 border settlements in the country (figure 8). These settlements are covered by various social support programs outlined in the Law of the Republic of Armenia on Social Support of Border Communities (Law of the Republic... 2014). Currently, support is provided to 82 settlements within 23 border communities.

Figure 8. Border settlements of the Republic of Armenia. *Source:* by V.G. Mkhitarian and G.G. Ghambaryan

Border settlements vary significantly from one another, highlighting the need for a territorially differentiated and targeted policy to address their specific needs effectively.

Therefore, territorial zoning will help identify problematic areas, reveal the causes and manifestations of regional development disparities, and facilitate the creation of policies aimed at establishing targeted competitive advantages. While equalization policies strive to create equal conditions across regions, policies focused on creating competitive advantages aim to foster opportunities for self-development, attract investment, and stimulate economic activity.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the study mentioned above, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- Global, regional, and local factors influence settlement patterns, creating a complex geographical mosaic of resettlement due to their multiplicity, varying priorities, and unique manifestations.
- Despite their unique characteristics, mountainous territories share similarities in settlement pattern features, trends, and challenges.

Characteristic Features of Settlement Pattern in Mountainous Territories:

- **Limited Productive Areas:** There is a scarcity of productive areas for economic development, leading to a dispersed and disproportionate distribution of population and settlements.
- **Population and Settlement Density Trends:** Population and settlement numbers and density decrease with increasing elevation.
- **Diverse Settlement Sizes:** Significant variability in settlement populations, with a notable proportion of abandoned, small, and medium-sized rural settlements.
- **Unique Migration and Demographic Processes:** Distinctive patterns of migration and demographic changes.
- **Functional and Ethno-Cultural Diversity:** High functional, productive, and ethno-cultural diversity and originality.
- **Varied Settlement Patterns:** A wide range of settlement patterns and layouts influenced by relief features.
- **Critical Role of Road Communication:** Roads play a crucial role in the territorial organization of settlements, characterized by uneven distribution, varying conditions, steep slopes, curves, and hazards.
- **Weak Road Connectivity:** Poor inter-settlement road connections and many isolated settlements due to terrain and road accessibility issues.
- **Compression of settlement pattern systems:** Settlement pattern systems in mountain countries are “compressed” spatially and temporally compared to those in plains.
- **Exposure to Natural Disasters:** Settlements in mountainous countries are often in high-risk zones for natural disasters, such as earthquakes, landslides, floods, mudflows and other geohazards.

Taking into account the peculiarities of the territorial organization of resettlement, typological zoning in mountainous countries can be distinguished as follows:

by the features of altitudinal zonation:

- Foothills valleys zone,
- Foothills regions zone,

- Mountainous regions zone,
- High mountainous regions zone;

by the features of impact zones of settlement pattern systems centers:

- Agglomeration zone,
- Suburban area,
- Peripheral zone of settlement pattern;

by the geographical location to borders:

- Internal zone,
- Border zone.

Summary

Thus, understanding the features of the settlement pattern in mountainous territories and conducting related studies not only holds cognitive significance but also provides a crucial information base for public administration and regional policy. Typological zoning based on settlement pattern features helps to clarify the trends and issues specific to each zone, thereby laying the groundwork for the development and implementation of measures aimed at improving and regulating these areas.

Mountainous regions, including Armenia, have often been characterized by a combination of so-called permanent “handicaps,” including low population density, underdeveloped infrastructure, remoteness from major markets, and fragile ecosystems (European Parliament 2016).

However, recent studies have shifted the perspective, viewing the physical characteristics of mountain areas not solely as negative factors but as “opportunities” and “strengths” that can be leveraged for sustainable development. This approach represents a significant shift in attitudes towards the perceived “weaknesses” and “threats” of mountain areas (European Environment Agency 2010; Debarbieux & Rudaz 2015; ADE 2012; ESPON 2014).

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